

DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED WEB-BASED ELECTRIC-MOTORCYCLE TRACKING AND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract

Operators of fleet of cars or motorcycles have challenges managing the drivers' behaviour, battery energy and security of their investment as well as personnel. This has heightened with the high rate of insurgency in Nigeria and many African countries. To address the afore-mentioned challenges, a tracking system is developed for an electric motorcycle to track the position, energy and driver's identity and behaviour making them available to a transport system administration on a secured web interface over a network. The device leverages a microcontroller sensor-based data acquisition system to sense the different parameters, web-based remote logging and Google Maps for determination of geographical location. Results obtained show the effectiveness of the developed system to track the electric motorcycle that was converted from a fossil fuel motorcycle. Previous literature has developed a combined tracking system for the position, energy and driver's identity to be used in electric vehicles, but this study differs because it implements the combined motorcycle. The work will promote security of lives, properties as well as provide a platform for planning, and administration of e-mobility devices as Africa prepares to transition from fossil fuel to the green economy.

Keywords: *Automation, electric-motorcycle, tracking system, GPS, energy tracking, personnel tracking*

1.0 Introduction

Electric mobility (EMs) entails any mechanically coupled machinery design that makes use of an electric motor, in conjunction with other propelling mechanisms rather than a fossil-fuel motor. They are designed for conveying people, animals and things from one geographical location or

point to another. Examples include e-motorcycles, e-cars, e-locomotives, e-bicycles and e-scooters, e-buses, e-craft, e-trucks, e-trams (Bilgin and Emadi, 2014).

Focusing on electric vehicles (EVs), which sometimes are referred to as battery electric vehicles (BEVs) they are automobiles that make use of one or more electric motors for propulsion (Alternative Fuels Data Centre, 2025; Majid and Ahmed, 2024). In general, it uses a large traction rechargeable battery pack to store electricity and to power the electric motor to cause movement and an auxiliary battery to power other accessories; it is usually plugged into a charging station or a wall outlet to charge the traction battery pack. This form of design is applicable to both heavy and light duty vehicles such as cars, trains, trucks, bikes, buses, aircraft and so on (Nasa Maxwell X-57).

Due to the vast growth of the adoption of EVs in some countries, governments like those of the United Kingdom and France have announced that in the year 2040, there will be no permission for the sale of internal combustion engines vehicles (ICEVs) also known as fossil fuel engines vehicles (FFEVs) anymore (GovUK, 2025). The advantages of e-mobility over internal combustion engine (ICE) technology include the fact that electric vehicles are often considered as an important element of climate change mitigation strategies because they do not emit greenhouse gases. They are also more reliable as they are prone to fewer breakdowns compared to ICE vehicles. They incur lower maintenance cost, comfortable, efficient and less complicated compared to ICE vehicles. EV disadvantages include higher price, lower range, lack of model variety, slow charging time, and lack of public charging stations and so on.

Different researchers have worked in different areas of EV development including tracking location, driving pattern, choice of route, and energy usage features for real world performance. This review will consider tracking location, driver behaviour, and energy of electric vehicles. It is aimed at synthesizing the key findings and insights from existing literature, identifying the latest trends/emerging technologies, and highlighting the challenges and future research directions.

Tracking the location of electric vehicles is essential for applications, such as optimizing charging infrastructure, understanding driving patterns, and monitoring fleet operations (Corchero *et al.*, 2014). Studies have analysed real-world electric vehicle usage data, including driving and charging patterns, to help develop future charging infrastructure and analyse the integration of electric vehicles into the power grid.

EV tracking technologies have evolved significantly, employing various methods to enhance location accuracy and user experience. These systems utilize a combination of GPS, GSM, and IoT technologies to provide real-time monitoring, which is crucial for both operational efficiency and safety.

Rokonuzzaman (2021) adopted a unique approach that lies in its comprehensive, targeted, and practical evaluation of PTCs (Path Tracking Controllers). It considered specific challenges in autonomous vehicle dynamics while integrating advanced control techniques and performance metrics. The article further addressed the problem of improving the functioning of PTCs for AVs (Autonomous Vehicles); it highlighted the need for exact, strong, and well-off path tracking in autonomous vehicles, considering the uncertainties in real-life driving scenarios. The limitations of the study include the simplifications in vehicle modelling, assumptions made during simulations, computational challenges of certain control techniques, robustness issues, and the potential for undesirable dynamics, which may affect the realistic application of the discoveries.

Nie *et al.* (2021) addressed accuracy in trajectory tracking and vehicle stability which is usually a challenge in intelligent vehicle tracking systems using ASSMC and hierarchical control structure for effective management of vehicle dynamics.

Su *et al.* (2022) not only considered the conventional controllers which is the longitudinal control approach but also considered lateral control to achieve better tracking accuracy as well as energy-saving output. The problem of trajectory tracking and optimizing for energy efficiency was solved by using a multi-objective model predictive control (MPC) strategy. There however still existed a need for adaptive adjustment of the weighting factor which corresponds to the different instances to enhance the performance of the system in a dynamic environment. The study may require a more reliable approach to perform the simulation of vehicle responses under critical road conditions.

Karim (2024) solved the problem of effectively detecting traffic incidents for proactive intervention and swift emergency response. The approach demonstrated a satisfying performance based on the accuracy and precision metrics. The study didn't consider environmental factors that have an effect on the working of the detection mechanism. Also, the performance of the YOLOv8 model depends deeply on the value and diversity of the training data set. While the advancements in EV tracking technologies present numerous benefits, they also introduce challenges that require careful consideration, particularly regarding privacy and integration with existing systems.

Monitoring driver behaviour is another critical aspect of electric vehicle tracking, as it can provide insights into factors that influence energy consumption, such as driving style, route choice, and charging habits. By understanding driver behaviour, researchers and policymakers can develop strategies to encourage more efficient driving and charging practices. Tracking driver behaviour is essential for enhanced road safety operations and improving vehicle performance. Various techniques have emerged, including deep learning models for real-time behaviour prediction, contactless communication systems, and multi-modal data collection platforms. These methods not only monitor driver actions but also assess vehicle performance, ultimately contributing to energy efficiency.

Al-Wreikat *et al.* (2021) evaluated the energy consumed by an EV using practical driving data obtained in Birmingham, UK, subsequent to a standard real driving test schedule (RDC/RDE) rather than just using unscheduled trips. This allowed for better reproducibility and comparison of results across different locations. The utilization of energy by an electric vehicle (EV) under real-world driving situations was evaluated, considering various features that can impact the consumption of energy, such as driving behaviour, ambient temperature, traffic conditions, and road rating.

Zhang *et al.* (2021) found that a connection-free (cordless) charging mechanism in combination with an eco-driving control approach at signalized intersections allow for good consumption of energy and promoting EVs is an innovation of this study. The work considered the optimization of driving behaviour of EVs that are incorporated with connectionless charging infrastructure by using efficient traffic management systems. Traffic conditions were deployed to enhance the driving range at defined areas. It was discovered that additional testing in various scenarios might be required to confirm the applicability of the model. It could also be observed that implementing the concept could pose practical challenges as a result of the difficulty that could arise from integrating wireless charging structures with existing urban transport systems.

Other consideration of this work was the distinct acceleration and deceleration profiles of EVs which were considered alongside other conventional petrol engines (Xu *et al.*, 2021). Apart from the aforementioned, the effect of EVs on traffic density specifically regarding their ideal acceleration and deceleration processes during traffic congestion was also considered. Traditional traffic models did not account for this distinct property of EVs compared to conventional vehicles thus leading to inaccuracies in traffic flow prediction and management. The data collected was from a specific region so the findings may not be applicable in its generality to other regions with different traffic conditions. It was also noted that varying human behaviour could introduce uncertainties that may not be captured in the model.

The authors in Vodovozov *et al.* (2021) unveiled the potential of intelligent braking controllers in order to enhance energy recovery during gradual and urgent braking scenarios. The work also proposed the application of findings from the fields of automation to improve braking control. The problem of addressing the highest energy recovery process during the application of brakes in electric vehicles was discussed. It considered devices and machinery that should be adopted to enhance the energy efficiency of different braking scenarios. These include the application of gradual braking and urgent braking cases. Battery-based sources were considered without looking at infrastructural and manufacturing emissions that affect the overall performance and adoption of EVs.

Gao *et al.* (2022) deployed innovative algorithms such as blockchain, and advanced deep learning rather than traditional diagnostic approaches for EVs. The work addressed key significant problems in fault analysis of electric vehicle charging equipment. These include; low accuracy in diagnosis resulting from the use of conventional methods, poor data processing and handling ability, and dependence on traditional processing expertise rather than intelligent diagnosis. Real-time data sets were used to inform practical applications of electric vehicle technology (Chou *et al.*, 2023) where the predominant behaviour of an EV was analysed by investigating the challenges of optimizing the health status of the lithium-ion battery. It addressed the relationship between the impacts of driving behaviour on battery life.

Ogidan *et al.* (2023) addressed the challenges of deploying an electric vehicle within the Elizade University gated campus community. An integrated approach was adopted which considered three distinct tracking parameters holistically, other than works that considered one or two parameters in isolation. It specifically cuts across people tracking, energy management, and location tracking for enhanced security and operational efficiency. The efficiency achieved as reported depends on the performance of the components (RFID, GPS Sensors) and the availability of internet connectivity. Failure in any aspect will affect the performance and reliability of the system.

Demirci *et al.* (2023), considered the behaviour of electric vehicle users and integrated it into vehicle to grid systems to harness its maximum potential. It applied the bootstrap method, which provided an optimal time interval for simulation thereby suggesting shorter time steps to yield results that are more precise and herein lies the novelty of the work. In addition, realistic datasets were considered using parameters such as charging location, duration, levels and timing. This includes the optimization of electric vehicle charging management to achieve a balanced supply and demand in the grid as well as support renewable energy sources.

In contrast, some argue that excessive monitoring may lead to driver anxiety or resistance, potentially undermining the intended safety benefits. Thus, a careful approach is necessary to ensure that data collection enhances rather than detracts from the driving experience. In the work

of Nie *et al.* (2021), the functionality of adaptive cruise control system was enhanced by making the driving experience to be closely related to human behaviour type with good user acceptance (Aguiri, 2022). The work addressed adaptive cruise control in electric vehicles by considering driver behaviour, through a model predictive control strategy that relies on deep reinforcement learning. This is to achieve an effective and user-friendly system, which can mimic human driving behaviour to accommodate individual driving characteristics and enhance the safe driving experience.

Electric vehicles' energy consumption is closely related to their performance and integration into the power grid. Research has investigated the impacts of electric vehicles on the electric power system, including the optimal placement and sizing of charging stations (Miri *et al.*, 2020). The core challenge handled in Miri *et al.* (2020) is the development of an accurate model for the estimation of the consumed energy by the EVs. This is crucial for improving the accuracy of EV range estimation and reducing "range anxiety" among drivers.

Ibrahim and Jiang (2021) carried out a comprehensive coverage of the energy system for electric vehicles, including both the stored and consumed energy aspects, with particular focus on lithium-ion batteries. The main problem solved in the work concerns the necessity for proper energy management for EVs to optimize their design and operation, particularly in terms of the stored and consumed energy systems. This will help to address the transportation sector's contribution to the global warming issue and greenhouse gas releases. New generation batteries like Li-S and Li-air have the potential for much higher energy density but currently face challenges with lifespan and safety that need to be addressed.

Sidharthan *et al.* (2021) focused on developing effective energy management strategies (EMS) for EVs that consider a wide range of factors that can affect the operation and battery life of the EV, including vehicle-related, driver-related, and environmental-related factors. Also discussed in the paper was the importance of using hybrid power sources, such as a combination of battery and supercapacitor (SC), to deal with the limitations of a single power source and make the overall performance and effectiveness of the EV better. It identifies several key issues with battery-powered EVs, such as limited range, battery life, and vehicle performance, and proposes the use of HPSS as a solution. Existing EMS did not adequately consider the impact of driving profiles, driver behaviour, traffic, and road conditions on battery life and capacity.

Mohammadi and Rashidzadeh (2021) investigated the management and storage of energy applied in EVs for smart cities. The work addressed the challenges of deploying IoT technology for Battery Management System's (BMS) efficiency. IoT sensors could present the charging status of the EVs, which is an efficient information-driven approach (Ogidan *et al.*, 2023). Major limitations of the study involve the control and monitoring of the energy storage device, the complexity of wired networks in Battery Management Systems and Network slowdown because of the diverse direction of data collection in WBMS.

Senthilkumar *et al.* (2021) considered battery monitoring for EVs to enhance battery life and safety. The work could predict battery life cycle and suggest optimal charging duration. It can ensure timely rent payment for battery charging, monitor battery parameters and log data for analysis. Drawbacks in this study include the existing battery technology limitations due to shortening lifespan and safety concerns, lack of battery monitoring infrastructures (in India) for EVs and reliance on timely payments for battery charging in existing methodologies. While the advancements in energy monitoring technologies present significant benefits, challenges remain

in achieving precise measurements and integrating these systems effectively. Addressing these issues is crucial for the future of EV energy management.

Table 1 below is a detailed comparative analysis of the quantities measured in e-mobility. It can be observed that previous literature have indicated measurement of battery power (Al-Wreikat *et al.*, 2021; Gao *et al.*, 2022; Miri *et al.*, 2020), vehicle position (Corchero *et al.*, 2014; Rokonuzzaman, 2021; Nie *et al.*, 2021), and drivers' behaviour (Al-Wreikat *et al.*, 2021; Xu *et al.*, 2021; Vodovozov *et al.*, 2021). While some consider measurement of more than one quantity (Al-Wreikat *et al.*, 2021), Ogidan *et al.* (2023) measure battery power, EV position and driver's behaviour for EV but the authors did not implement the design on the vehicle.

Therefore, this study advances knowledge by proposing the measurement (tracking) of battery power, vehicle position, drivers' behaviour, and its implementation in an electronic motorcycle. The rest of the paper is arranged in the following manner. Section 2.0 is the methodology; section 3.0 focuses on results and discussion. The paper concludes with section 4.0.

2.0 Methodology

Figure 1 is the architecture of the system. It comprises a GPS sensor (A9G GSM/GPRS module), power sensor (PZEM 017) and the RFID-based driver identification sensor. The three sensors are connected to the Esp 2286 microcontroller which is the heart of the data acquisition system. The information received from the sensors are displayed on a LCD and logged to a remote server which is made available to system administrators in real-time through a secured web interface.

The block diagram above illustrates how the various components communicate. The system is divided into two main modules: the **hardware module** and the **software module**.

2.1 Sensor-based Data Acquisition

The hardware module consists of an RFID reader, a wireless microcontroller, and a GPS module. These components were programmed in the Arduino Independent development Environment using the embedded C programming language.

The **RFID reader** scans cards assigned to users.

The **wireless microcontroller** transmits the scanned data to the web server for validation.

Upon receiving a response from the server, the microcontroller determines whether the user is authorized to access the system (in this case, the vehicle).

If the verification is successful, the **GPS module** begins collecting location data at specified intervals and transmits it to the microcontroller.

The PZEM017 energy module measures the power in the battery and sends measured data to the microcontroller

The microcontroller then logs the GPS data, along with the vehicle occupant's information and energy data to the web server.

Table 1: Comparative analysis of the quantities measured in e-mobility

Paper	Tracking of battery power	Tracking of position	Tracking of driver's behaviour	E-mobility Type
Corchero <i>et al.</i> , 2014				E-Vehicle
Rokonuzzaman 2021				E-Vehicle
Nie <i>et al.</i> , 2021				E-Vehicle
Su <i>et al.</i> , 2022				E-Vehicle
Al-Wreikat <i>et al.</i> , 2021				E-Vehicle
Xu <i>et al.</i> , 2021				E-Vehicle
Vodovozov <i>et al.</i> , 2021				E-Vehicle
Gao <i>et al.</i> , 2022				E-Vehicle
Demirci <i>et al.</i> , 2023				E-Vehicle
Nie <i>et al.</i> , 2021				E-Vehicle
Miri <i>et al.</i> , 2020				E-Vehicle
Ibrahim and Jiang, 2021				E-Vehicle
Sidharthan, <i>et al.</i> , 2021				E-Vehicle
Mohammadi and Rashidzadeh, 2021				E-Vehicle
Senthilkumar <i>et al.</i> , 2021				E-Vehicle
Ogidan <i>et al.</i> , 2023				E-Vehicle
Developed tracking system				E-motorcycle

Figure 1: System Architecture

Figure 2 a) RFID and GPS data acquisition circuit, b) RFID and GPS data acquisition circuit on breadboard

Figure 3: Block Diagram of the battery power data acquisition

Figure 4: Components of the battery power data acquisition (DAQ) system

2.2 Description of Operation of the Energy DAQ Module

The module consists of PZEM-017, Shunt Resistor (100A), Serial to RS485 converter, esp8266 and i2c 20x4 Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) module. PZEM017 is an energy sensor module manufactured by PeaceFair and designed to measure voltage, current, power, and energy consumption in electrical circuits. It was designed to measure current flowing in circuit (usually for high current of 50A, 100A, 200A etc) with a combination of a shunt resistor of the same ampere rating or higher than the battery being used. This module measures the Current in Amperes (A), Voltage in Volts (V), Energy in Joule (J), and Power in Watts (W) being consumed by the load (Electric Motorcycle). Esp8266 (an IoT microcontroller board) reads these values from the sensor through the RS485 converter and displays these values on the 20x4 i2c LCD screen. Also, it sends real time data (sensor's values) to the cloud in order to be viewed on the developed web platform.

2.3 Web-based Remote Data Logging

This comprises a web application hosted on a web server and the web interface as shown in Figure 9. The web server through a wireless communication receives the data from the three sensors (RFID, GPS and PZEM017 energy sensor) (Ogidan et al., 2022) and makes them available to the user. The server provides an interface accessible via the Internet, enabling a **monitoring station** to view real-time and historical data which can be viewed on a secured web interface. This includes **real-time vehicle tracking** on a map. The system also maintains historical records for **analysis and reporting** purposes. The web server was developed using Php/MySQL while the web interface was developed with HyperText Mark-up Language (HTML) and Cascaded Style Sheet (CSS).

2.4 Description of the Motorcycle under Consideration

In order to accomplish the objectives of this work, a motorcycle that was previously converted from fossil-power to electric-power is used. The power and torque of the electric motorcycle is estimated as 1.84HP and 3.02Nm @ 3481.1 rpm. For a probable distance of 15km and using a deep cycle battery, a 12V 100AH is selected based on the estimated value of 0.68unit battery. Details of the design specifications and actual selection are provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Specifications of electric motor and battery for the electric motorcycle

Parameters	Design estimate	Design selection
Rated Power	1.84 Hp or 1.38 KW	2 Hp or 1.4914 KW
Rated Torque	3.02 Nm	3 Nm
Rated Voltage	12 V	12 V
Number of Battery	0.68	1
Power Factor	1	1
Rated Speed	3481.1 rpm	3600 rpm

The converted electric powered motorcycle is shown in Figure 5. The mounted electric motor connected to the wheels of the scooter is shown in Figure 6. This enables the electric motor to be powered by the battery and hence it propels the electric motorcycle. Figure 7 shows the interfacing of the electric motor and battery with the tracking system. This arrangement allows real-time data capture for tracking energy and location.

3.0 Results and discussion

3.1 Testing the E-motorcycle with the Developed Tracking Device

The experiment setup is as shown in Figure 5 during which the developed e-motorcycle tracking system was interfaced with an e-motorcycle and measurements were obtained regarding the geographical position, battery power and drivers' record. Figure 8 is the LCD Output of the power data acquisition (DAQ) system. Figures 9 and 10 are the geographical position of the e-motorcycle on Google Maps and the driver's record shown on the web interface, respectively.

Figure 5: Electric motorcycle (EM); converted from fossil-powered engine

Figure 6: Electric motorcycle (EM); showing electric motor mounted and connected to the wheel

Figure 7: Experimental setup of the Data Acquisition System with the electronic motorcycle

Figure 8: LCD Output of the power data acquisition (DAQ) system

Figure 9: Geographical Position of the E-motorcycle on Google Maps

Figure 10: Web interfacing output of the driver's record

Discussion of Results

This work is an ongoing research and presents preliminary results of interfacing a microcontroller-based tracking system with an electric motorcycle. Results obtained from Figure 8 revealed a current of 115.24A, voltage of 7.19V, 828.50W power and an energy of 7.00J as shown in the LCD. This is an on the site information about the energy status of the electrical motorcycle to assist the rider (driver) plan his activities. However, this same energy information would be made available to the transport system administrator on the web interface over the Internet which assists in monitoring of the motor cycle remotely and to aid planning and allocation of resources. From Figure 9, the geographical Position of the E-motorcycle on Google Maps is shown.

In a similar manner, Figure 10 is a web interfacing output of the driver’s record including name (Adesina Adebayo), vehicle model (Toyota Corolla), device unit (w366G), card user identification (226C301A). The information about the geographical location of the electric motorcycle made available in real time on the web interface to the system administrator serves as a tool for remote monitoring in safeguarding the lives of rider (driver), passengers and the assets of the organisation. The ability of the system to identify the rider (driver) through and RFID-enabled unique identification could assist the process of transparency and accountability in driver’s scheduling, and route allocation. Table 3 is a comparison report of this study and Ogidan et al., (2023). From Table 2, it could be observed that this study is able to address the measurement of very high current up to 100 A; whereas Ogidan *et al.*(2023) was designed for lower current rating. Shunt resistor is employed in this work as a means of diverting the high current so that the energy that could have been detrimental to the operation of the microcontroller is dissipated through the shunt resistor. This type of circuitry was not used in Ogidan *et al.*(2023).

Table 3: Comparison of the developed e-motorcycle tracking system with Ogidan et al., (2023)

Parameter	Developed e-motorcycle tracking system	Ogidan et al., (2023)
Designed	Designed for electric motorcycle	Designed for electric vehicle
Implementation	Implemented with an e-motorcycle	Not implemented on an e-mobility device
Current level	Used to measure high current up to 100A	Used to measure low current as low as 3A
Additional circuitry	Shunt resistor circuitry was included for power compensation	No Shunt resistor circuitry was included

4.0 Conclusion

In this study, a tracking system for electric motorcycle (EM) was developed and implemented to measure (track) the geographical position of the EM, power and driver identity. For the tracking process, a microcontroller-based multi-sensory data acquisition system was developed and connected to the EM that was previously converted from fossil-power to electric-power. Experimental results obtained reveal the ability of the developed tracking device to display the current and voltage of the EM battery through a LCD, while records of the drivers' identity and geographical position of the EM were logged over a secured web server and displayed on a web interface and Google Maps respectively. Future work would involve performance evaluation of the developed tracking system both at single-user and multi-user scenarios as well as obtaining data about the EM for different and wider geographical locations over the Internet.

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Conflict of interest

The authors do not have any conflict of interest

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